

Bees, Ants and Fireflies: How mimicking social insects and nature inspired engineering are driving intelligent WFM solutions as part of Agent X

An HGS Digital white paper

Sharath Tadepalli

Director and Global Practise Leader for Data Sciences and AI

HGS Digital

Austin, TX

LEVERAGING ADVANCED AI AND ML FOR AGENT TASKING IN COGNITIVE CONTACT CENTERS

Executive Summary

Scheduling tasks to manpower and expecting them to do their jobs optimally, like the travelling salesman problem, has long been questioned, researched, and analysed to test for operational posterity. Not every person responds to a job assignment productively despite being qualified to do the job. Ignoring employee psychometric scores, we observe that not every individual performs well in situations of high pressure and demand. Not everyone is welcoming to taking orders and commands. Discarding assumptions of job apprehensions, personal affiliations, inter-personal communications

skills and rapport between employees and across hierarchies, when we define a community or an eco-system as a self-regulating self-conditioning entity that works together and cohesively for a common good, then an individual aberration in performance can be covered up with other community members pitching in.

Biases of assignments, bad or no pattern matching an agent to a domain/language/switch or predispositions of agents towards or against an account all add up to bad work productivity numbers. Add in the constraints of shifts, time slots and time zones, these problems then keep getting multiplied and compounded. Pile on the pressures of KPIs like reduced AHT numbers and increased CSAT and NPS scores, agents hence work under immense duress to fruitfully comply with their works scheduled while being contributors.

Schedule adherence and tardiness via disciplinary and regulatory issues start to creep in and payable but non-billable work activities take a hit. Non-payable work that generate goodwill like community outreach programs go for a toss and agents only regard “on-call at-desk” work as priority and nothing else matters. Call triage queues also cause strain on the workers thereby reducing the quality of their outputs as reflected in their monthly audit scores.

How do we solve this age-old problem of optimal schedules and optimizing work force management through intelligent, quantifiable, and measurable resource allocation?

How do we set standards, derive benchmarks, and formulate individual goals? How does a floor team leader assign duties optimally to meet an account demands while an RTA design schedules for effective employee engagement rather than increased revenue generation? How do we have an informed R&R program hence? How do C&B plans evolve through employee assignments when “group-knows-better” thinking becomes the foundations for new team KRAs and “common-good” become the new individual KPI norms?

Introduction to Nature Inspired Engineering

To help us mitigate these problems, we at HGS digital have drawn heavily from nature inspired algorithms including firefly algorithm, artificial bee colony algorithm and ant hill colony algorithm to render intelligence to the scheduling problem.

In addition we have introduced several modern machine learning methods to the study including archetypal analysis, anomaly detection, abnormality detection, novelty detection, market basket analysis, association rule mining, RFM & RFD analysis to impute intelligence to the entire floor management activity of team leads and RTAs in the contact center paradigm.

Metrics evolved hence are now tangible and deterministically mensurate for a periodic, holistic, and unbiased review of account management, audit trails, agent performance scoring and individual/group appraisals, thereby moving away from traditional scoring and review systems based on speculative goals, subjective opinions, and stochastic surveys.

How do these techniques work?

As part of mimicking behavior of beehive colonies or firefly mating procedures or ant colony production lines, we impart artificial intelligence to the models built on real world data that assumes role-based assignments for a community good rather than individual brilliance. The motto being a team of good, loyal, and dedicated players who listen to instructions and take commands always wins over a team of stars with egotistical individuality and self-centric decision making. However, individual brilliance is not ignored and is aptly rewarded via equitable weighting mechanisms, where applicable.

Additional knowledge from aforementioned techniques for group segmentation and micro-targeting help understand the “individual” aspects of the crowd to cater for more direct attention. It is easier to treat a person in a crowd for unacceptable behavior based on group standards, much like how the animal kingdom corrects an erring member in pride.

Industry Applications and Opportunities

The scope here is not just limited in and to a contact enter scenario. Even in mundane activities like assigning household chores to shift assignments for doctors/nurses in hospitals, matching teachers to grades, to patrolling policemen to night guards to delivery personnel, scheduling seamlessly finds connect in modern age, across the spectrum wherever a supply-chain or goods/service transfer transaction is involved.

Functioning like a chain of ants or like a flock of bees or as a swarm of fireflies provides for group intelligence and near real-time feed-forward or backward propagating errors and warnings (read pheromones based bio-chemical messages in the animal world), something very akin to deep learning techniques.

The HGS Digital Approach

Prior market research identified substantial gaps in data science infused intelligence in WFM solutions, both custom made as well as in COTS. Some of the key technology comparisons are encapsulated in the in the table below:

Metric	Hierarchy	Business Use	Value Addition	Notes	Category	Algorithm(s)
Conduct a TS analysis for projected usage of time for next week, fortnight, month and quarter	Agent	Individual appraisal of time forecasted for usage going forward	Will help agents chalk out their engagement plan vis-a-vis holidays, vacations etc.		Usage Assistant	Time series - since it is still < 1 year, we will use ARIMA, ETS, BATS, TBATS, ARCH, GARCH, SARIMA; after 1-year data, drop GARCH and add HW.....Add I TS forecasts of leaves and holidays for interpolation
Repeat with pivoting on switch/LOB	TL	Line managers have an informed view of expected traffic per LOB and corresponding resource allocation	Informed scheduling especially for seasonal data. Classical WFM tools will not predict seasonality, trend and cyclicity of data		Planning Assistant	TS
	RTA	Upper level managers can track usage per account for billing and revenue purposes	Forecasting future earnings will help deliver financial performance per account for informed decision making with respect to staffing and resource management		Planning Assistant	TS
Optimization of accumulated hours per switch	TL	Line managers now can pattern match which agent performs well (productive) against which switch/account and assign resources intelligently	Classical and COTS WFM tools do not pattern match but allocate resources by available time slots, experience levels etc.	AHT, TAT and other performance metrics need to be shared	Optimization and Matching Assistant	RFD
Custom definitions to track Schedule adherence, Absenteeism and Tardiness	Agent + TL	Line Managers will have an informed view on customised metrics such as in-office shrinkage, paid shrinkage, unpaid shrinkage, absenteeism (Out-of-office shrinkage) etc.	Much more granular view of agent metrics will enable TL to rank agents based on these metrics.		Regulation Assistant	
Swap Recommendation engine	Agent	Agent will have information on Top performers in their team with whom they can swap shifts in order to maintain quality of work.	Reduces Time for TL; Pattern match for the right swap will ensure work quality is not compromised.	Intensity metric from below	Swap Assistant	Decile rank
	TL	TL need not approve swapping on the application as long as listing adherence is maintained			Swap Assistant	Decile rank violations
Optimization of best hours/slots for agent performance	TL	Pattern match agents with their most productive slots	Informed scheduling based on agent's past performance where scheduling accounts for peak productivity hours.	AHT, TAT and other performance metrics need to be shared. $AHT \times TAT \times \text{Billed hours} = \text{Intensity for ABC algorithm}$	Optimization and Matching Assistant	ABC
Optimization of schedule based on holiday and leave trends	Agent	Scheduling will take holidays and leaves into account	Informed scheduling will save TL's time in approvals.		Optimization and Matching Assistant	TS based Interpolation
Schedule optimisation given propensity for higher productivity	TL	Based on productivity levels of the agent, pivoted on accounts, we can schedule work activities (training, KT etc.)	Agents productivity disposition towards certain accounts will be weighed higher reflecting in informed schedule optimisation.	Firefly algorithm	Optimization and Matching Assistant	FFA
Star performer - plan growth	RTA	Chart out a growth pattern for star performers	COTS do not offer multi-disciplinary approach to agent/resource mapping keeping in mind intangibles like individual career goals	While firefly can provide star performers, we can use ant hill and honey bee to diversify their roles with new KPIs targeted at career growth at an individual level	Star Chart	$RFM \Rightarrow FFA + ACO$
Cross train	RTA	Inventory high - pattern match with productivity, training status and schedule	COTS does not leverage existing resources for cross-training for cross-staffing when schedules permit/ open-up	Possible outcome from above	Training Assistant	ABC
Help with flexible scheduling given floor availability	TL	Do not pigeon-hole agents into single shifts and within-shift work hours but have an informed WFM so that no one feels they have to work the graveyard hours consistently	COTS offer customizations but not informed algorithm driven approaches	Possible outcome from above	Scheduling Assistant	ACO
Behavioural analysis	RTA	Let us look at $AHT \times TAT \times \text{Billable hours}$. Let us figure out novelties, anomalies, outliers and extremities here. What do they tell us? If we presume, $AHT = F/R$, $TAT = R/F$ and Billable hours = M and conduct an RFM analysis, we can categorize agents into graded workers for educated C&B + R&R programs	COTS do not offer such diverse thinking or intuition based models	Extremities, abnormalities, outliers and anomalies	Knowledge Assistant	Archetypal analysis, RRFC, Isolation forest, RFM models and one-way SVMs
Propensity analysis	RTA	Look at options to see which 2/3 LOBs - voice + voice or voice + social care or social care + social care, can be clubbed for scheduling at an agent level given performance data	COTS do not offer such diverse thinking or intuition based models	MBA, PBA etc.	Knowledge Assistant	Association rules

We at HGS Digital Data science lab, introduced these concepts to the WFM team spread across 7 geographies catering to a multitude of clients across numerous domains. We propagated the scope of artificial intelligence through these approaches via a prototype design based on a BFSI account currently served by our Jamaica team in a voice-only English-only 24x7x365 support system.

What we promised as palpable business benefits include –

A case study on experimenting with our homegrown solution in a contact center in Jamaica

We noted the following aspects of the study before designing the models for the prototype –

- Voice support only
- 256 personnel
 - 234 Agents, 18 TLs and 4 RTAs
- 15630 records
 - 26 variables

- Standard statistical assumptions made
- Holidays and Activities data used sparingly
- Schedules data not available

The following Custom KPI assumptions were made:

- Paid duration = Billable amount
- AHT = PaidDuration/100
- ACW lies between 1-3 mins
- TAT = AHT-ACW
- Std. work hours = Activity A billed at x\$ per hour
- OT = Activity B, C and D billed at 1.5 x per hour
- CSAT & NPS scores = Decile grouping of AHT values
- Total Billing = actual + overtime (> 480 mins)

Variables included – Worked Minutes, Scheduled mins, Paid Duration, Unpaid Duration, loginlate, leftearly, etc.

Operational and practical assumptions made included –

- Unpaid duration < 15 = Break
- Unpaid duration $\geq 15 < 30$ mins = Activity C
- Unpaid duration ≥ 30 mins = Activity D
- Activity A: If Paid duration ≥ 480 then 480 else Paid duration
- Activity B: If Paid duration ≥ 480 then Paid duration - 480 else 0
- Activity C: If Unpaid duration between 15 and 30 mins then Unpaid duration else 0
- Activity D: If Unpaid duration ≥ 30 mins then Unpaid duration else 0
- Raw CSAT scores go from 1 to 10

- Raw NPS scores range between -100 to 100
- Total Billing = (Activity A * x)+(Activity B * 1.5x)+(Activity C * 1.5x)+(Activity D * 1.5x) where x = 1
- Shift 1: 8:00 AM-4:00 PM, Shift 2: 4:00 PM -12:00 AM, Shift 3: 12:00 AM-8:00 AM
- Performance Index = 0.5 *(aht + csat + nps + tat) + 0.5 * total_billing (customisable)

Tech Stack proposed to be developed included plug-and-play modules that are compatible with existing commercial WFM solutions:

- Usage Assistant
- Swap Assistant
- **Knowledge Assistant.....cutting edge solutions**
- Optimization and Matching Assistant
- Planning Assistant
- Regulation Assistant
- Scheduling Assistant
- Training Assistant
- Star Chart

Tech Stack : Python, R, AI, ML, Deep Learning, SQL Database

Key Business Need:

A centralized view of account related staffing, specific grievances, progress of agents, monitoring of activities and other attributes under one umbrella was lacking in the traditional way of management overview. A disparity by region, switch, domain, and account caused for erratic and mismanaged agent attrition levels, imbalanced revenue streams, biased forecasting patterns and uninformed action points. The lack of ability to

juxtapose vertically across geographies or horizontally across accounts or switches resulted in a vortex of unusable data.

Specific exploratory intervention of the data science unit resulted in preliminary findings seen below, allowing for a globalised and standardised schedule-centric KPI view of a dedicated account, and for a world-wide (HGS family) audience -

AHT by Time of day

X-axis	Month_Yr
Y-axis	aht
Colours	dayname

Actionable attributes, and their Implications:

On imposing various machine learning, applied statistics and advanced AI models on the data set, numerous apparent outcomes, discernible patterns, and not-so-obvious findings were deciphered as explained below. These results were realised at a group level and broken down to an agent level granularity to better understand and explain community vs. individual entity behavior in a herd setting where equitable weightage is given to both tendencies.

Use Case - Identify agents who set performance benchmarks

employee_id	Total_Activity_A	Total_Activity_B	Total_Activity_C	Total_Activity_D
<chr>	<dbl>	<dbl>	<dbl>	<dbl>
J07454	457.6892	98.51667	15.28250	0.00000
J03468	480.0000	239.57351	13.42175	12.09035
J07674	457.7500	66.77125	13.85125	3.81875
J08060	475.6047	66.50933	15.68733	18.89533
J04793	472.6006	76.71936	14.99106	40.79680

Variables - Activity A, Activity B, Activity C, Activity D

Algorithm used - Archetypal Analysis

Business consumption - Set performance extremities and records; Forms a basis for identifying optimal activity combinations based on propensity

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Use Case - Identify novel/unique agent performance

EMP_Code	aht	tat	total_billing
J05649	4.882314815	3.882315	36162.83
J07578	4.667166154	3.667166	41314.49
J07597	4.691065574	3.691066	38141.37
J07732	4.435795588	3.435796	38017.87
J07774	4.871308197	3.871308	37067.95
J07888	4.833608333	3.833608	38509.01
J07891	4.816640625	3.816641	40827.19
J07892	4.739658571	3.739659	40087.87
J07909	4.63868254	3.638683	41240.75
J08043	4.620629508	3.62063	39078.81
J08047	4.599238182	3.599238	35729.96
J08049	4.726907692	3.726908	40992.56
J08053	4.886197015	3.886197	43401.15

Variables - aht, tat and total billing

Algorithm used - One Way SVM

Business consumption - Identify propensity of individuals to certain accounts by their two-way relatively outstanding (other worldly) performance - good or bad

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Use Case - Anomaly detection

	employee_id	aht	nps	csat	tat	total_billing	paidduration	Performance_Index	scores	anomaly
6	J01553	7.0	-100	1	4.0	47747.185	39525.03	23829.5925	-0.004123	-1
14	J03468	7.0	-100	1	4.0	50024.820	41015.69	24968.4100	-0.015355	-1
20	J03866	7.0	-100	1	4.0	58091.845	46826.47	29001.9225	-0.182426	-1
36	J04817	5.0	-50	4	2.0	13776.035	10292.81	6868.5175	-0.000908	-1
42	J05256	6.0	-100	1	3.0	2271.885	1853.91	1090.9425	-0.035952	-1
47	J05530	5.0	50	8	4.0	8130.010	6675.89	4098.5050	-0.012658	-1
62	J05645	6.0	-100	1	3.0	6554.580	5569.49	3232.2900	-0.003196	-1
74	J05862	3.0	100	10	2.0	482.600	313.07	298.8000	-0.032349	-1
76	J05864	8.0	-100	1	5.0	898.125	758.75	406.0625	-0.044196	-1
93	J07334	6.0	-80	2	3.0	1353.300	1164.28	642.1500	-0.042084	-1
95	J07336	4.0	75	9	3.0	17110.220	12119.90	8600.6100	-0.002019	-1
109	J07443	7.0	-100	1	4.0	52550.205	41035.13	26231.1025	-0.144064	-1
122	J07580	4.0	100	10	3.0	415.630	415.63	266.3150	-0.074199	-1

Variables used - Performance Index

Algorithm used - Isolation Forest

Business consumption - Identify individuals who can absorb or who will buckle under the load of sudden and unplanned spike in traffic or pressures of extra/hostile agent work

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Use Case - Anomaly (Abnormality) detection

	employee_id	aht	nps	csat	tat	total_billing	paidduration	Performance_Index	scores	anomaly	avg_codisp
20	J03866	7.0	-100	1	4.0	58091.845	46826.47	29001.9225	-0.182426	-1	37.0
135	J07671	6.0	-80	2	3.0	59249.840	44148.80	29590.4200	-0.189532	-1	28.0

Variables used - Performance Index

Algorithm used - Robust Random Cut Forest

Business consumption - Identify individuals who will not conform to rules/laws/policies and who are most likely to cause change but yield high performance.....they are to be tapped as technical tutors/mentors/floor leaders etc.

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Use Case - To recommend people for activity changes or activity swaps

Popular	antecedents	consequents	antecedent support	consequent support	support	confidence	lift	leverage	conviction
0	(Activity_C)	(Activity_D)	0.508547	0.824786	0.504274	0.991597	1.202247	0.084831	20.850427
1	(Activity_C, Activity_A)	(Activity_D)	0.508547	0.824786	0.504274	0.991597	1.202247	0.084831	20.850427
2	(Activity_C)	(Activity_A, Activity_D)	0.508547	0.824786	0.504274	0.991597	1.202247	0.084831	20.850427
3	(Activity_B, Activity_C)	(Activity_D)	0.508547	0.824786	0.504274	0.991597	1.202247	0.084831	20.850427
4	(Activity_C)	(Activity_B, Activity_D)	0.508547	0.824786	0.504274	0.991597	1.202247	0.084831	20.850427
5	(Activity_B, Activity_A, Activity_C)	(Activity_D)	0.508547	0.824786	0.504274	0.991597	1.202247	0.084831	20.850427
6	(Activity_B, Activity_C)	(Activity_A, Activity_D)	0.508547	0.824786	0.504274	0.991597	1.202247	0.084831	20.850427
7	(Activity_C, Activity_A)	(Activity_B, Activity_D)	0.508547	0.824786	0.504274	0.991597	1.202247	0.084831	20.850427
8	(Activity_C)	(Activity_B, Activity_A, Activity_D)	0.508547	0.824786	0.504274	0.991597	1.202247	0.084831	20.850427
9	(Activity_D)	(Activity_C)	0.824786	0.508547	0.504274	0.611399	1.202247	0.084831	1.264672
10	(Activity_A, Activity_D)	(Activity_C)	0.824786	0.508547	0.504274	0.611399	1.202247	0.084831	1.264672

Optimal	antecedents	consequents	antecedent support	consequent support	support	confidence	lift	leverage	conviction
48	(Activity_C)	(Activity_A)	0.359649	0.855263	0.302632	0.841463	0.983865	-0.004963	0.912955
49	(Activity_A)	(Activity_C)	0.855263	0.359649	0.302632	0.353846	0.983865	-0.004963	0.911019

Metrics used - Performance index at activity level

Algorithm used - Market Basket Analysis (Association Rule Mining)

Business consumption - Forms a basis for approving/disapproving requests for activity swaps

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Use Case - An informed way to approve, disapprove, automate a request for shift swap

J01296 Shift 2

employee_id	Shift	Performance_Index	Decile
J07443	Shift 2	387.6757	10
J08210	Shift 2	382.3493	10
J07280	Shift 2	382.3359	10
J05238	Shift 2	381.4023	10
J07737	Shift 2	380.6818	10
J07449	Shift 2	379.2287	10
J07336	Shift 2	379.2101	10
J03468	Shift 2	376.9681	9
J05537	Shift 2	376.3706	9
J07339	Shift 2	374.1563	9
J01553	Shift 2	372.1225	9
J07671	Shift 2	371.3824	9
J07909	Shift 2	369.3795	9

Metrics used - Performance index at shift level

Technique used - Decile Ranking

Business consumption - Is an informed way of recommending best talent (not best available) to be a like-to-like or a better replacement. Forms the basis for approving/disapproving a shift swap

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Use Case - Identify sub-optimal performance/assignment

employee_id	Frequency	Recency	Duration	r_quartile	f_quartile	D_quartile	RFD_Score
J05530	4.768493	3.768493	6675.89	4	4	4	444
J05535	4.850742	3.850742	9216.41	4	4	4	444
J05659	4.35935	3.35935	871.87	4	4	4	444
J05699	4.589753	3.589753	8720.53	4	4	4	444
J07775	4.635683	3.635683	5562.82	4	4	4	444

Variables - AHT, TAT and Duration

Algorithm used - RFD Analysis

Business consumption - Forms a basis to study and approve/disapprove assignment change - measures propensity/suitability towards an account

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Use Case - Identify top agent performance

employee_id	Frequency	Recency	Monetary	r_quartile	f_quartile	m_quartile	RFM_Score
J03475	5.665818	2.665818	40192.14	1	1	1	111
J04784	5.650538	2.650538	39759.97	1	1	1	111
J07682	5.614198	2.614198	37044.7	1	1	1	111

Variables - AHT, TAT and Total Billing

Algorithm used - RFM Analysis

Business consumption - Forms a suitability-based performance metric for R&R programs

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Use Case - To find the top performers with respect to the activities: consequently, to make optimal and near-optimal assignment or change the activity assigned

employee_id	Activity	aht	nps	csat	tat	total_billing	Performance_Index	optimum.value.min	optimum.value.max	assignment
J05533	Activity_A	6	-75	3	3	1920.000	928.5000	4736.0	10232.5	Near-Optimal
J05533	Activity_C	6	-75	3	3	0.000	-31.5000	7420.0	12624.0	Needs improvement
J05533	Activity_D	6	-75	3	3	498.930	217.9650	682.0	12074.0	Near-Optimal
J05535	Activity_A	5	50	8	4	8499.970	4283.4850	4784.5	12840.5	Near-Optimal
J05535	Activity_C	5	50	8	4	51.660	59.3300	13330.0	14722.0	Sub-Optimal
J05536	Activity_C	6	-75	3	3	68.955	2.9775	3073.5	8162.0	Near-Optimal
J05537	Activity_A	4	75	9	3	17921.030	9006.0150	8523.0	11740.5	Optimal
J05538	Activity_C	4	100	10	3	22.680	69.8400	9074.0	9296.0	Needs improvement
J05538	Activity_D	4	100	10	3	0.000	58.5000	50.5	8882.0	Optimal
J05539	Activity_A	3	100	10	2	5653.280	2884.1400	5396.0	11804.5	Near-Optimal
J05539	Activity_B	3	100	10	2	77.595	96.2975	13919.0	15422.5	Sub-Optimal
J05544	Activity_A	4	100	10	3	767.750	442.3750	2767.0	11383.5	Near-Optimal
J05545	Activity_B	6	-75	3	3	3229.890	1583.4450	217.5	11564.0	Optimal
J05579	Activity_B	5	0	6	3	4310.055	2162.0275	14215.0	15213.5	Needs improvement
J05579	Activity_D	5	0	6	3	6377.235	3195.6175	2683.5	3221.0	Optimal

Variables used - Performance index at activity level

Algorithm used - Firefly Algorithm

Business consumption - Studies the effect of activities on performance indices given prior engagements

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Use Case - To find the best performance relative to a day, week number, shift and activity. Consequently, to make optimal and near-optimal assignment or move people around

employee_id	week_number	dayname	Shift	Activity	Performance_Index	optimum.value.min	optimum.value.max	assignment
<chr>	<chr>	<chr>	<chr>	<chr>	<dbl>	<dbl>	<dbl>	<chr>
J00999	2020-30	Saturday	Shift 1	Activity_A	195.0000	181.5	432.0	Optimal
J00999	2020-31	Thursday	Shift 1	Activity_B	87.7400	253.5	452.0	Needs improvement
J00999	2020-31	Thursday	Shift 1	Activity_C	-44.5000	392.0	664.5	Needs improvement
J00999	2020-32	Wednesday	Shift 3	Activity_B	58.2150	590.5	598.0	Sub-Optimal
J00999	2020-32	Wednesday	Shift 3	Activity_C	-45.0000	-26.5	17.5	Near-Optimal
J00999	2020-32	Wednesday	Shift 3	Activity_D	0.1725	255.5	516.5	Needs improvement
J00999	2020-33	Saturday	Shift 1	Activity_A	194.5000	330.0	420.5	Near-Optimal
J00999	2020-33	Saturday	Shift 1	Activity_B	-32.8100	201.0	243.5	Needs improvement
J00999	2020-33	Saturday	Shift 1	Activity_C	-45.5000	367.5	517.0	Needs improvement
J00999	2020-35	Friday	Shift 2	Activity_C	-45.0000	273.0	612.5	Needs improvement
J00999	2020-35	Friday	Shift 2	Activity_D	-0.1350	475.5	506.0	Sub-Optimal
J00999	2020-35	Monday	Shift 1	Activity_A	196.5000	261.5	517.0	Near-Optimal
J00999	2020-35	Monday	Shift 1	Activity_B	250.5600	380.0	491.5	Near-Optimal
J00999	2020-35	Saturday	Shift 3	Activity_C	-45.0000	445.0	540.5	Sub-Optimal
J00999	2020-35	Tuesday	Shift 2	Activity_B	62.7750	180.5	199.0	Near-Optimal

Variables used - Performance index at week number, weekday, shift and activity

Algorithm used - Artificial Bee Colony Algorithm

Business consumption - Studies the effect of temporal parameters on performance indices given prior assignments

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Use Case - Identify community and individual KPI's

Metrics	Ideal Values
AHT	8.821195
CSAT	3.061904
NPS	-88.3195
TAT	1.705875
Total_Billing	54.25789

employee_id	aht	nps	csat	tat	total_billing
J07581	8.6495	0	6	3.140857	480
J07585	8.5858	-50	4	2.333167	480
J07888	12.7355	50	8	3.833608	480
J07907	8.6353	-50	4	2.468603	480
J07907	8.5108	-50	4	2.468603	480
J08048	9.0192	-50	4	2.375091	480
J08048	9.085	-50	4	2.375091	480
J08048	8.7612	-50	4	2.375091	480
J08051	12.6472	25	7	2.956194	480
J08167	9.329	-50	4	2.4734	480

Variables - AHT, NPS,CSAT,TAT, Total Billing

Algorithm used - Ant Colony Optimisation (275 Generations)

Business consumption - Identifies individuals KPIs for improvement; Forms a basis to understand community averages for minimum acceptable thresholds to be set

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Use Case - Shift reassignment recommendation using ACO

	Row Labels	Average of csat	Average of total_billing	Average of tat	Average of aht	Average of nps	Optimal aht	Optimal Billing	Optimal TAT	Optimal NPS	CSAT	Parameter Outperformance	Recommendation
J00999	Shift 1	1	474.9878	3	6.666666667	-100	8.821195	54.25789	1.705875	-88.3195	3.06	2	No Swap
	Shift 2	1	468.92	3	5.666666667	-100	8.821195	54.25789	1.705875	-88.3195	3.06	2	No Swap
	Shift 3	1	480	3	6.833333333	-100	8.821195	54.25789	1.705875	-88.3195	3.06	2	No Swap
J01005	Shift 1	1	480	4	7.2	-100	8.821195	54.25789	1.705875	-88.3195	3.06	2	No Swap
	Shift 2	1	480	4	8	-100	8.821195	54.25789	1.705875	-88.3195	3.06	2	No Swap
	Shift 3	1	480	4	7.5	-100	8.821195	54.25789	1.705875	-88.3195	3.06	2	No Swap

Variables - AHT, NPS,CSAT,TAT, Total Billing

Algorithm used - Ant Colony Optimisation (275 Generations)

Business consumption - Identify parameter-based high performance across shifts and recommend reassignment/approve change request if count equal to 5 or leave it to TL's discretion if count is 3 and 4 and recommend NO change otherwise

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Use Case - Weekday/Weekend reassignment recommendation using ACO HGS digital

employee_id	Weekday	Average of aht	Average of total_billing	Average of tat	Average of csat	Average Nps	Optimal aht	Optimal Billing	Optimal TAT	Optimal NPS	CSAT	Parameter Outperformance	Recommendation
J00999	Wednesday	6.33333333	480	3	1	-100	8.821195	54.25789	1.705875	-88.3195	3.06	2	No Swap
	Friday	6.33333333	480	3	1	-100	8.821195	54.25789	1.705875	-88.3195	3.06	2	
	Monday	7.33333333	480	3	1	-100	8.821195	54.25789	1.705875	-88.3195	3.06	2	
	Saturday	5.33333333	447.81556	3	1	-100	8.821195	54.25789	1.705875	-88.3195	3.06	2	
	Thursday	6.66666667	480	3	1	-100	8.821195	54.25789	1.705875	-88.3195	3.06	2	
	Tuesday	6.33333333	480	3	1	-100	8.821195	54.25789	1.705875	-88.3195	3.06	2	

Variables - AHT, NPS, CSAT, TAT, Total Billing

Algorithm used - Ant Colony Optimisation (275 Generations)

Business consumption - Identify parameter-based high performance across weekdays and weekends and recommend change/approve change request if count equal to 5, leave it to TL's discretion if count is 3 and 4 and recommend NO swap otherwise

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Use Case - Additional training for personal growth HGS digital

employee_id	Activity	aht	nps	csat	tat	total_billing	Performance_Index	optimum.value.min	optimum.value.e.max	assignment
J02927	Activity_B	6	-75	3	3	6953.835	3445.4175	6187.5	1457.5	Optimal
J03475	Activity_A	6	-75	3	3	27125.81	13531.405	12489.5	15305	Optimal
J03475	Activity_B	6	-75	3	3	7754.025	3845.5125	583.5	5372.5	Optimal
J03475	Activity_C	6	-75	3	3	49.95	-6.525	13990	3457.5	Near-Optimal
J03475	Activity_D	6	-75	3	3	5262.36	2599.68	7689.5	2876.5	Near-Optimal
J04784	Activity_A	6	-75	3	3	27441.43	13689.215	16968	2676	Optimal
J04784	Activity_B	6	-75	3	3	7997.535	3967.2675	4649	4761	Near-Optimal
J04804	Activity_A	6	-75	3	3	19598.74	9767.87	14662.5	10674.5	Near-Optimal
J04804	Activity_B	6	-75	3	3	6378.375	3157.6875	16718.5	6909	Near-Optimal
J04804	Activity_D	6	-75	3	3	4778.49	2357.745	14979	157	Optimal
J05247	Activity_A	6	-75	3	3	25996.9	12966.95	13424.5	4329.5	Optimal

Emp_ID
J02927
J03475
J04784
J04804
J05247
J05632
J05639
J05861
J06920
J07582
J07673
J07682
J07782
J07877
J07878
J07907

Variables - AHT, NPS, CSAT, TAT, Total Billing

Algorithm used - RFM + FFA

Business consumption - Identifies individuals who can be recommended for training/certifications or sponsored programs for personal growth without negatively effecting existing assignments

| 19

Use Case - Forecasting worked minutes (Daily, Weekly, Monthly) HGS digital

Variable - Worked_Minutes

Algorithm used - ETS, Arima, TBATS And Neural Nets

Business consumption - Schedule employee roster/availability based on team daily, weekly and monthly “worked minutes” forecasts

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Use Case - Forecasting worked minutes (Weekday and Bi-Weekly) HGS digital

Variables - Worked_Minutes

Algorithm used - ETS, Arima, TBATS And Neural Nets

Business consumption - Schedule employee roster/availability based on team weekday and bi-weekly forecasts

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Use Case - Holiday shortfalls - day, week and month HGS digital

Date	employee Count	Worked_Hours	Average	Worked_hours_Average	Delta	Recommendation
01-08-2020	92	736	116	928	192	Status Quo
08-08-2020	70	560	116	928	368	Status Quo
19-10-2020	190	1520	116	928	-592	Shortfall: Hire Temp workers
26-12-2020	2	16	116	928	912	Provide More leaves
01-01-2021	1	8	116	928	920	Excess

- a) Holidays
- b) Holidays (Month)
- c) Holidays(Week Number Wise)

Month	Worked_Mi nutes	Forecasted	Recommendation
August	169613		
September	1430447		
October	1094972		
November	855494.1		
December	820717.4	921889.4	Excess: Provide Leaves

Week Number	Actual	Forecasted	Recommendation
46	319327.9	-	
47	219725.4	-	
48	167120.3	-	
49	317544	-	
50	368199.2	-	
51	215602.1	-	
52	0	258182	Excess: Provide Leaves
53	0	258182	Excess: Provide Leaves

Variables - Employee Count, Worked_Hours

Algorithm used - ETS

Business consumption - Hire contractual workers in case of shortfalls and schedule less agents in case of surplus

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Use Case - Regulation assistant HGS digital

Current

- Number of instances of Late Login
- Number of instances of Early Logout
- Number of instances of Unscheduled Absenteeism
- Number of instances of Activity A < 480 mins
- Number of instances of Activity B < Community mean
- Number of instances of Activity C < Community mean
- Number of instances of Activity D < Community mean

Future

- Number of instances of unnecessary shift swapping
- Number of instances of Loss of Pay

employee_id	month	login_late	left_early	unsch_abs	Activity_A<480	Activity_B<Mean	Activity_C<Mean	Activity_D<Mean
J00999	2020-08	0	0	0	0	1	5	5
	2020-09	9	0	0	1	2	21	19
	2020-10	2	0	0	1	1	14	14
	2020-11	0	0	0	0	0	8	7
	2020-12	0	3	0	0	0	7	7
	2021-01	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
	2021-02	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
J01005	2020-09	0	0	0	0	0	2	2
	2020-10	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
	2020-11	2	0	0	0	1	8	6
	2020-12	0	0	0	0	0	9	9
	2021-01	0	0	0	0	0	13	13
J01013	2020-09	1	0	0	0	0	3	2
	2020-10	0	0	0	0	1	1	1
	2020-11	0	2	0	0	2	6	5
	2020-12	0	2	0	0	2	8	6
	2021-01	0	0	0	0	0	9	9

Business consumption - Line Managers will have an informed view on customized metrics such as late logins, early logouts, absenteeism, etc.

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Summary and The Force of Impact:

- Ground truth verification is pending from our colleagues in the Caribbean but we forecast a 70–80% increase in operational KPIs at an individual and a group level with our intervention.
- An easy to read reference guide for the panners has been compiled via the summary sheet below for informed and directed decision making.

No.	USE CASE	Algorithm	BENEFITS	END USER
1	Identify performance benchmarks	Archetypal Analysis	Highlight record and trend setters in the team/account to set up benchmarks. Can be used for monthly/quarterly/mid-year/annual R&R programs	TL/RTA
2	Novel associates performance	One Way SVM	Identify extreme propensity to accounts for individuals	TL
3	Identify anomalous performance	Isolation Forest	Identify associated propensity to handle heavy traffic/high wok pressure demands	TL/RTA
4	Identify abnormal performance	RRCF	Identify change makers in the crowd to be part of decision making-floor management-tech leadership roles	TL/RTA
5	Activity recommendation	Association Rules	Recommending activity changes without loss of productivity	TL/RTA
6	Shift swap recommendation	Decile Ranks	Automating the process of shift swap	Agent / TL

No.	USE CASE	Algorithm	BENEFITS	END USER
7	Sub-optimal performance identification	RFD Analysis	Reassignment of tasks / activities	TL
8	Identify top performers	RFM Analysis	Recommended associates for quarterly/mid-year/annual C&B programs	TL/RTA
9	Identify performance benchmarks based on the activities	FFA	Scheduling work activities based on past performances by studying effects of activities on individual performances	TL/RTA
10	Identify performance benchmarks based on the week number, weekday and shift	ABC	Pattern match associates with most productive slots/accounts	TL
11	Identify acceptable minimum across each of the parameters	Ant Colony optimisation	Identifying associate's performance KPIs at granular level vis-à-vis community minimum acceptable thresholds	Agent/TL
12	Identify associates whom the company can nurture and invest in	RFM->FFA + ACO	Recommended associates for personal career growth	TL
13	Planning associates' schedules based on forecasted work	Time Series Analysis	Planning schedules on daily, weekly, bi-weekly, monthly, quarterly and seasonal work	Agent / TL

No.	USE CASE	Algorithm	BENEFITS	END USER
14	Forecast holiday shortfalls in productivity	Time Series	Reassignment of tasks / activities based on increase in working hours or shortfall on daily, monthly and weekly basis	RTA
15	Weekend/Weekday reassignment recommendation	ACO	Recommend/Approve associates for day reassignment provided their productivity levels match/exceed personal averages across days	TL/RTA
16	Shift reassignment recommendation	ACO	Recommended/Approve associates for shift reassignment provided their productivity levels match/exceed personal averages across shifts	TL/RTA
17	Regulatory assistance	Data base management tools-	Line Managers will have an informed view on customized metrics such as late logins, early logouts, absenteeism, etc.	TL/RTA

With regards to deployment, we envisage the following functionalities to be available offline vs. near real-time:

Deployment

Offline/Post event diagnostics

- WFM via scheduling assistant
- Forecasts via planning assistant
- Star Charts
- Select aspects of knowledge assistant
- Training Assistant

Real Time/Near Real Time

- (Shift) Swap Assistant
- Regulation Assistant
- Usage Assistant
- Activity - Shift - Week day - Week end - Account reassignments (needs one time prior data analysis) via knowledge assistant
- Queue pattern matching (needs one time prior data analysis) via optimization and matching assistant

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Let us talk Business:

- The proposed solution is planned to reduce disciplinary issues by 95%.
- The proposed intervention is anticipated to completely eradicate informal buddy-buddy mode of shift swaps.
- We expect a 50% rise in CSAT and NPS scores and a 60% rise in ESAT numbers.
- We estimate individual training attendance, participation, and performance to increase 3x.

- We predict a 30% reduction in AHT, Talk Time and ACW numbers and a 30% increase in TPH numbers.
- We project a 75% improvement in QA audit scores.
- We speculate a 90% increase in job variety through activity diversification and uniquely quantifying each activity as an equitable contributor to an individual KPI.
- We envisage a 50% increase in CX levels through customer being matched to the right agent via the call type, call summary and call driver.
 - We prognosticate a 50% reduction in repeat callers or call escalation.
- We anticipate an indirect benefit of up to 15% reduction in attrition numbers.
 - We envision a 33% reduction in costs of training and retention.
- We gauge a 40% increase in cross-sell and up-sell numbers for out-bound calling.
- We prophesise a 45% increase in operational revenues due to right sizing and right assigning of resources.

The X Factor:

- A distinctive and unparalleled solution
 - Innovative and unique
- In-house solutions
 - No external dependencies
- Cloud enabled and optimized
 - Scalable and repeatable
 - Modular, trainable, and customizable
 - Plug-and-Play
- Offline or Real-Time
- Secure
- On-prem or Cloud deployment

Why HGS Digital?

Many large-cap firms are consciously collecting massive amounts of demographic, transactional, ancillary, and collateral data from across cooperative omni-channels, subject to regulatory frameworks and legal obligations.

HGS Digital, following this lead, has been at the forefront of such an endeavor. By investing in its Data Science and Analytics program, HGS Digital has built a diverse portfolio of customized solution development and deployment, across multiple industry verticals and domains:

- Media
- BFSI

- FMCG
- CPG
- Telecom
- Healthcare
- Pharma
- E-Commerce
- Automotive
- HR Analytics
- Retail Analytics
- Marketing Analytics
- Operational Analytics
- Sales Analytics
- Content and Viewership Analytics
- Survey Analytics
- Telecom Analytics
- Social Media Analytics
- Financial Analytics
- Geoanalytics

HGS Digital's Data Sciences unit developed face mining solution stands-out in this regard with its abilities in:

- Thorough data cleansing and preprocessing in the signal space
- Seamless on-site deployment
 - Accurate isolation and labeling of discernible patterns
 - Robust anomaly and outlier detections
 - User-friendly GUI based controls
 - High standards of security and privacy
- Developing and listing editable, trainable, and customizable libraries
 - Unhindered access to statistical models driven by in-house designs
 - Fine-tuning weights and parameters of various ML libraries based on automatic error minimization
 - A comprehensive evaluation of models on 100s of imaging data sets for facial recognition
 - Custom hybrid modeling leveraging expertise from transfer learning modules
- Being computational optimized and cost moderate
- Operationally friendly based on feedback received in UAT reports
- Periodic updating and upgrading and keeping abreast of the latest advances in ML and AI technologies

About HGS Digital

HGS Digital is a marketing, data science, and technology consulting and services provider that has helped various teams within 100+ organizations with digital transformation and automation solutions. Through our data-driven services, we help customers select the right models and systems and implement a complete strategy that helps teams get higher ROI out of their existing investments.

Our Data Practice has a matured and diverse portfolio, supported by big data experts who help clients successfully strategize and implement data-driven solutions within their organization. By integrating the right data from different systems, we help clients understand their customers better. Through AI- and ML-based data modeling, analysis, reporting, and visualization, we are able to provide our clients with timely and highly valuable and actionable insights.

Disclaimer:

Any information taken from or referenced to this paper should be credited to the author and HGS Digital.